

Greek teachers' beliefs model questionnaire on teaching and learning

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Abstract

The objective of this study is to develop a reliable and valid questionnaire for the assessment of teachers' beliefs about teaching and learning, in conjunction with their attitudes towards the curriculum. The preliminary phase of the study employed 38 items from the international literature on the teacher profile and effective teaching, which were subsequently classified into four themes. A total of 628 active primary and secondary school teachers employed in Greece completed the questionnaire. In order to guarantee the internal consistency and validity of the questionnaire, modifications were made at each stage of its construction. The final version of the Teachers' Beliefs Model Questionnaire to Teaching and Learning (TBMQ_TL) comprises 27 items that assess four domains related to teaching and learning by investigating teachers' philosophical profile and their attitudes towards the curriculum.

Keywords: *Teacher Beliefs; Self-Assessment; Learning Theories; Curriculum Implementation; Questionnaire.*

JEL Classification: I21; I28; C83.

1. Introduction

Since 2011, educational reform in Greece has placed a premium on the evaluation of educational processes and teachers. Contrary to being a mere accountability mechanism, teacher evaluation is an inherently self-reflexive process (Peterson, 2000) that enables educators to gain insight into their own skills and improve their teaching effectiveness. A core component of this process is the investigation of teachers' beliefs, as these internal perspectives significantly determine professional competence—the combination of knowledge, attitudes, and motivations applied in the classroom (Airasian & Gullickson, 1997; Keller & Duffy, 2005). Proficiency can be defined as the skills, knowledge, attitudes, and motivational variables that are the main source of knowledge when approaching such situations (Epstein & Hundert, 2002; Kane, 1992; Klieme, Hartig, & Rauch, 2008). These skills, knowledge, attitudes, and motivational variables are not innate, but are learned and therefore taught. The term "occupational competence" represents a conceptual approach to its application in professional life, particularly in professional disciplines in which the interaction of knowledge, skills, attitudes and motivation play a special role (Epstein & Hundert, 2002; Kane, 1992; Weinert, 2001). A crucial element of effective pedagogy is the ability of teachers to adapt their approach in alignment with the specific needs and abilities of their learners (Mawer, 1995; Protheroe, 2004). The evaluation process is an indispensable component of effective teaching, as it facilitates student progress and establishes teachers as credible professionals (Graham, 2008). Furthermore, the advent of educational technology has had a profound impact on the learning process, particularly in terms of communication, resource accessibility, and opportunities for teacher professional development. The present study hypothesizes that self-assessment can be employed as a tool for evaluating teachers' performance regarding teaching standards (Blank, 2002). Within the Greek educational system, although there has been continued reform in the sector, there is as yet no standardized tool that can be used to evaluate the pedagogical beliefs of teachers alongside their views towards curriculum design and curriculum implementation. This absence gives rise to a theoretical and practical gap. On the one hand, empirical research on the relationship between epistemological orientations and curriculum attitudes is not fully covered due to the absence of a combined measurement framework. Conversely, practitioners do not possess a systematic self-assessment tool that can facilitate reflective practice and professional growth (Katsarou & Dedouli, 2008).

The present study aims to address this gap by developing and validating the Teachers' Beliefs Model Questionnaire on Teaching and Learning (TBMQ_TL), a novel instrument designed to collect empirical data on teachers' beliefs regarding teaching and learning. The distinguishing feature of this study is that it operationalizes the beliefs of teachers as professionals, as informed by the main learning theories, and their attitudes to curriculum, simultaneously, within a psychometric concept that has been designed to meet the requirements of the Greek educational setting. The

combination of epistemological construct with the curriculum perceptions provides the study with a more in-depth insight into the professional profile of teachers.

The objective of this research is to develop and validate a reliable and theoretically grounded self-assessment instrument capable of capturing distinct pedagogical orientations (behaviorism, radical constructivism, and social constructivism) alongside curriculum-related beliefs. This approach contributes to the advancement of measurement theory in education and the practical enhancement of teacher self-evaluation processes.

2. Learning theories

The selection of Behaviorism, Social Constructivism, and Radical Constructivism as the theoretical pillars upon which the TBMQ_TL is founded is a deliberate academic decision. These theoretical approaches represent the broad spectrum of instructional practices found in modern classrooms, ranging from guided, incremental instruction to learner-centered discovery and social negotiation of meaning. The comprehension of these theories enables educators to select and implement teaching methods that are consistent with curriculum principles, thereby ensuring that their practices effectively support learning objectives and foster professional development.

2.1 Behaviorism

Behaviorism is one of the most significant theoretical approaches to the study of human learning and development. It emerged in the early 20th century, emphasizing observable and measurable behavior as an object of scientific study, while disregarding internal mental processes. The theoretical framework underpinning behaviorism is predicated on the notion that behavior, in its observable form, is shaped by positive or negative reinforcement. The process of learning, as defined by this theoretical framework, occurs when an individual associates a specific stimulus, predominantly from the environment, with a predetermined response. Emotions, thoughts or intentions are not considered necessary for understanding behavior. The behavioral approach has been demonstrated to be effective in acquiring simple skills, learning basic concepts or procedural steps, and implementing activities in special education, and also in digital environments (Skinner, 1953; Anderson & Dron, 2011). This learning theory supports guided and incremental instruction, whereby each step is learned through feedback and repetition. An exemplification of this is the learning of pre-learning through repeated questioning and immediate correction of errors. The implementation of planned teaching with teaching material structured in small steps with continuous monitoring and immediate feedback is also supported by this learning theory (Slavin, 2020). An example of such software is educational software that provides immediate feedback on whether the response is correct or not and subsequently guides the student to the next step. Behavioral contracts, which are agreements between teacher and student regarding specific behavioral targets and corresponding rewards, are also employed. Furthermore, classroom management systems are utilised. Examples of such systems include the use of whiteboards, grading systems, or colored cards to provide immediate feedback on behaviors. However, critics have noted that Behaviorism does not focus on higher cognitive functions and treats learning (mainly) as a mechanistic process, emphasizing the environment rather than the individual (Woolfolk, 2019).

2.2 Social constructivism

Social Constructivism is predicated on the notion that individuals construct their knowledge actively by interacting with their socio-cultural environment and others. According to this theory, learning is a social process that occurs within the context of culture and society. In this paradigm, language assumes a pivotal role as a medium of communication and a conduit for the negotiation of meaning, thereby influencing the structuring of knowledge. The notion of knowledge being co-constructed through dialogue, cooperation and shared experiences is central to this theory. In essence, Social Constructivism posits that knowledge is constructed through social interactions involving exchange and comparison. The social environment of learning is regarded as structured. The structure of an organized school environment, and in particular a classroom, provides all the conditions so that, as Applefield et al. (2000) state, participants in the educational process can refine their meanings and then help others to seek meaning. Gergen (1994) has proposed a modified design in terms of both scientific research and educational practice, promoting social investment as opposed to individual investment. In the educational process, this theory is applied through collaborative learning. Students are invited to work in groups, share ideas and build knowledge collectively. Dialogue is the main method through which argumentation is developed and learning is facilitated. To illustrate this, one may consider a discussion on the phenomenon of gravity, wherein students are tasked with sharing their experiences of dropping objects in their

everyday lives. This approach underscores the learner's role as a participant in knowledge construction, with the educator functioning more as a facilitator, guiding, supporting, and encouraging exploration and discovery (Jonassen, 1999; Garrison & Vaughan, 2008). However, this theoretical framework occasionally overlooks the personal aspect of learning. Additionally, the intricacies inherent in the management of collaborative groups can present a substantial challenge for educators when confronted with issues such as the potential for unequal participation, wherein certain students exhibit a disproportionate reliance on more proficient peers.

2.3 Radical constructivism

Radical constructivism can be regarded as an evolved form of classical constructivism. This radical reinterpretation of knowledge was developed by Ernst von Glasersfeld. According to this theory, knowledge does not reflect an objective reality; rather, it is entirely subjective, i.e. a personal construction based on individual experiences. This standpoint asserts that knowledge is not a precise mirror of reality, but rather an individual's unique conceptualization influenced by their personal experiences. The concept posits that reality is a construct of the mind, and the objective of learning is not to attain a "correct" representation of reality, but rather to construct knowledge that is functional and useful for survival and action in the world. The capacity for communication and coordination among individuals within a society is contingent upon the alignment of these personal constructions. The application of radical constructivism engenders a profound respect for the personal perspective of each student. It is predicated on the acceptance of the heterogeneity of solutions to a given problem, and the understanding of education as being predicated on investigation and argumentation as opposed to the finding of the "right" answer. The cultivation of critical awareness and the capacity for reflection and self-regulation are further emphasized (Karagiorgi & Symeou, 2005).

In terms of the application of theory to the learning process, teachers are encouraged to facilitate the development of personal interpretations and to provide support through collective discussion, without the need to emphasize "correct" outcome. Nevertheless, the implementation of this theoretical framework in educational settings has been met with criticism, which alleges an exaggeration of the relativity of knowledge and a concomitant undermining of the concept of scientific truth. It has been argued that this approach can lead to the adoption of cognitive relativism, where all perspectives are viewed as subjective and, consequently, all views are considered valid. However, this is not always deemed appropriate within scientific or pedagogical contexts.

Conversely, an understanding of learning theories empowers educators to select and implement teaching methods that are consistent with the principles of the curriculum. This, in turn, ensures that teaching practices effectively support learning objectives and promote the desired learning experience. Consequently, this enhances teachers' ability to reflect on their practices and make informed changes. This, in turn, fosters a culture of continuous professional development and enhancement in teaching. The integration of learning theories and curricula has been demonstrated to facilitate the adaptation of teaching to the varied needs of pupils. As learning theories provide guidelines for how students learn best, teachers are able to design lessons that respond to individual differences and promote equity in education. Concurrent exploration of learning theories and curricula is conducive to the development of evidence-based educational policies and practices. This facilitates the establishment of education systems that are characterized by flexibility, adaptability, and a commitment to enhancing the quality of education.

At the same time, curriculum functions as the formal articulation of educational aims, content choice, teaching methods, and evaluation systems. But the implementation of curriculum is not an empty concept; implementation is filtered through the belief systems of teachers (Lomas, 2017). The extent of consistency or dissonance between epistemological inclination and the curriculum form can interfere with the instructional faithfulness, adaptation procedures, and experience of effectiveness. In this way, the analysis of curriculum perceptions and learning theories will make it possible to have a multidimensional view of teacher professionalism between personal belief systems and school systems.

3. Objective and research hypotheses

The research team intended to develop a valid self-assessment model. Its significance lies in the establishment of criteria for self-assessment of teaching effectiveness as perceived by in-service teachers. These criteria are based on evidence from a realist literature review concerning effective teaching. The development of such criteria is of paramount importance, particularly in Greece, where there are no teacher standards to support the development of evaluation tools. The realist review method is particularly suited to areas such as medicine and education, where findings from

randomized controlled trials can be pooled to determine whether a new treatment or intervention actually improves outcomes (Greenhalgh et al., 2011).

The following hypotheses are posited in the current study: (a) Responses in the TBMQ_TL would provide insight into the extent to which teachers' beliefs, as derived from existing literature, are retained. (b) The TBMQ_TL would exhibit clearly defined factors with adequate fit indices.

For all stages of the research, ethical approvals were obtained from the Greek Ministry of Education in 2017. Some elements of the broader research project (excluding the present findings) have been published elsewhere, but are not referenced in this manuscript in order to preserve the anonymity required for peer review. Although the data collection was conducted in 2018, the findings remain highly relevant as the core beliefs of Greek teachers and the underlying structures of the national curriculum have not undergone radical shifts in the intervening years. Furthermore, this manuscript focuses specifically on the psychometric validation of the tool's structure, representing a distinct and necessary phase of a broader research agenda.

4. The first phase

The initial phase of the study involved determination of the key dimensions and important aspects of the questionnaire. This was done in order to facilitate the subsequent testing of the number of items selected through this process in the following stages of the research.

In the context of the realist review of the literature, the following statements are drawn from the questionnaire entitled "The Emerging Theory / Philosophy of Teaching and Learning" (Sass, 2003) and from texts from the Pedagogical Institute and the volumes of Matsagouras (2011) and Bagakis (2004). 38 items were initially identified and classified into two thematic units (learning theories, curriculum) and five subunits related to the following categories of effective teaching: 1. Learning theories (three subunits – 24 items): This concept is applicable to both the radical and social constructivist approaches to learning, as well as to behaviorism. 2. Curriculum (2 subunits – 14 items). Teaching flexibility encompasses the potential for alternative evaluation, relevance, and availability of learning resources, the utilisation of contemporary pedagogical approaches, and the autonomy afforded to educators, the suitability of teaching methods, the realism of lesson objectives, and the integration of cross-disciplinary content. Impressions of the curriculum from the perspective of students encompass their diverse needs, pupils' creativity, students' daily routines, the fostering of positive social interactions, sufficient time, and the degree of acceptance by students.

Figure 1. Units and Subunits (phase 1)

The items selected were subjected to a process of item clarity review guarantees the validity with the assistance of six teachers. This process, which was conducted in person, involved the presentation of the items in question. The comments were duly considered and certain items were rephrased, while others were entirely removed and new items were introduced. This process was deemed essential as certain items were deemed to be repetitive, expressing the same idea, while others were absent from a specific thematic unit. In both instances, the questionnaire required either condensation or supplementation.

The modified questionnaire was then presented to a further 14 teachers for re-examination in order to ascertain its clarity of meaning and ease of understanding. As no further comments or recommendations were received, the questionnaire, comprising 38 items from two thematic areas, was subjected to a content validity check using the structured content analysis (Weber, 1990). This was deemed necessary as content validity is used to ascertain whether and which factors are capable of measuring the intended construct.

This procedure was conducted by a panel of seven experts, comprising three university professors (a professor of literature, a professor of statistics, and a professor of pedagogy) and four teachers (two from primary and two from secondary education). The utilization of expert content analysis is pivotal in ensuring that the questionnaire's inquiries comprehensively and accurately encapsulate the multifaceted nature of the concept or phenomenon under investigation. This is of particular importance when dealing with abstract or multidimensional concepts such as "educational effectiveness" or "learning engagement". Experts are able to identify ambiguities, ambiguous wording, or technical errors in the questions. Their contribution is instrumental in enhancing the clarity, precision, and comprehensibility of the questions for the intended audience. Furthermore, the expertise of a team of specialists can facilitate the identification of questions that may contain cultural biases or prove to be inappropriate for specific population groups. This process ensures the cultural sensitivity and equity of the tool. Furthermore, experts can assess the relevance of each question to the objectives of the survey and the extent to which the set of questions fully covers the scope of the study.

The involvement of experts in the evaluation of the questionnaire guarantees the validity of the tool and its general use in scientific research. When it comes to research that needs to gather data, such tools – whose deployment has been supported for such a purpose by the experts' review – are judged to be valid and reliable.

A pilot testing of the questionnaire was undertaken with 42 primary and secondary school teachers assigned to different subject areas. The data obtained from this pilot application has been subjected to testing and analysis using the Jamovi 2.3.28 statistical package. In particular, the Cronbach alpha coefficient was employed to ascertain the reliability of the measurements. This coefficient represents a measure of the internal consistency of the variables that the survey is designed to represent as a new extracted factor. The values of Cronbach's alpha were acceptable to have a value greater than .70.

5. Second phase

The study's objectives in the second phase were on the assessment of the constructed validity and internal consistency of the five factors and the thirty-eight TBMQ_TL items, the determination of which was an outcome of the initial process. In addition, the objectives for this phase were to assist in identifying research blindness, its solution, and capturing the potential research threat.

Multistage sampling was used. Specifically, a stratified approach was adopted based on the type of school units, followed by random selection of schools using official lists provided by Regional and Local Education Authorities across different prefectures and municipalities. The TBMQ_TL Questionnaire was given out to six hundred twenty-eight teachers (220 male and 408 female) with the assurance that they could discontinue participation at any stage of the project and that their identity would never be revealed in any subsequent publications. Two hundred and eighty-three of the participants were employed in primary schools, while 345 were employed in secondary education. The participants responded to each item on the questionnaire using a 5-point Likert scale, with responses ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree).

6. Data analysis

A Principal Component Analysis (PCA) with Varimax rotation was conducted to determine the factor structure of the questionnaire. The process of item selection and purification followed the classic methodological framework proposed by Churchill (1979), ensuring that only items with high validity and clear factor loadings were retained. This approach strengthens the methodological grounding of the scale and ensures its reliability for future use in educational research. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a statistical technique that is used to identify the number of factors to be interpreted (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007) and to quantify the importance of each factor, thereby describing the variability of a data set. The selection of Principal Component Analysis (PCA) combined with Varimax rotation was deliberate and guided by specific methodological and interpretive considerations. PCA was preferred over Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) primarily due to the exploratory nature of the initial stage, aiming at dimension reduction and simplification of the data structure. PCA effectively identifies underlying dimensions (factors) while maximizing the

explained variance, making it particularly useful for the initial exploration of complex constructs, such as teachers' beliefs. Varimax rotation, a widely used orthogonal rotation method, was chosen specifically because it simplifies the interpretation of factors by minimizing cross-loadings. It achieves this by maximizing the variance of squared loadings within each factor, thus clearly delineating which variables belong strongly to each factor. This clarity in factor structure is essential in educational research, where distinct and clearly interpretable factors significantly enhance the practical utility of measurement tools. Alternative methods, such as oblique rotations (e.g., Oblimin), allow for correlated factors. However, in this research, theoretical assumptions suggested distinct and independent constructs (behaviorism, radical constructivism, social constructivism, and curriculum). Thus, orthogonal Varimax rotation aligned more closely with the theoretical framework and the aim of developing clearly distinguishable dimensions, facilitating practical applicability and interpretability in educational contexts. Moreover, Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) subsequently validated this orthogonal factor structure by testing whether the data adequately fit the theoretically proposed uncorrelated factors, further confirming the appropriateness of this methodological choice.

The initial principal component analysis (PCA) revealed five factors with 38 items in the TBMQ_TL, which collectively accounted for 55.67% of the total variance. Some additional items exhibited low loadings (less than .35) or demonstrated loading on multiple factors. A further principal component analysis was then conducted, with the data from the previous phase excluded. The results indicated the presence of four factors, comprising 27 data points, which collectively accounted for 51.72% of the total variance. The data loading ranged from .625 to .794, as illustrated in Table 1. As posited by Hair et al. (1995), an acceptable solution should account for at least 60% of the total variance. Furthermore, the nature of the scale, which is being employed for the first time with teachers in Greece, demonstrates a satisfactory percentage (Coakes & Steed, 1999). The KMO adequacy was .875, indicating that the present data set is suitable for PCA, with values between .80 and .90 generally considered desirable (Kaiser & Rice, 1974). Similarly, the Bartlett sphericity test yielded a statistically significant result ($p < .001$), indicating that the variables exhibited sufficient intercorrelations to justify proceeding with the analysis. The final iteration of the 27-item questionnaire comprises four thematic sections. The first section, labeled "behavior", contains five items, while the second, "radical constructivism", contains seven. The third section, "social constructivism", contains five items, and the fourth section, "curriculum", contains ten items. The latter section includes the previously identified sub-factors "Impact on teaching" and "Impact on students" following the principal component analysis (PCA) conducted in the second phase.

Table 1. Rotated component matrix

	Components			
	1	2	3	4
Students need praise, good grades, or other rewards in order to learn effectively.			0.704	
Learning occurs when there is a measurable change in student behavior.			0.681	
For the most effective learning, students' errors should be minimized and successes maximized.			0.686	
Learning is growing through the accumulation of information.			0.720	
Students learn best when they have the opportunity to observe a demonstration or example of what is being taught.			0.707	
The best learning occurs when students discover answers for questions and problems themselves rather than having the answers told to them.		0.652		
It is important to help students organize their thinking by teaching them general concepts (or schemes) before they learn more specific information.		0.636		

Meaningful learning occurs when students mentally create knowledge structures (schemes or concepts) by combining new ideas with their prior knowledge (existing schemes or concepts).	0.704
Learning involves conscious decision-making.	0.719
Teachers must be active knowledge mediators.	0.645
Learning is based on students' mental processes.	0.711
Teachers should plan the teaching so that students learn in simple, forward-looking steps.	0.723
The teacher should be a facilitator of learning rather than a presenter of knowledge.	0.690
Students can be trusted to find their own goals and should be given choices as to what and how they will learn.	0.625
Learning increases through interaction with others.	0.694
Collaborative learning is an effective way to enhance student learning.	0.742
Teaching offers meta-cognitive skills.	0.633
It caters to the different needs of all students.	0.659
It is appealing to the pupils.	0.732
It promotes positive social relations.	0.794
The activities proposed are related to students' daily life.	0.743
It offers alternative assessment capabilities.	0.688
The learning and information sources defined are adequate, appropriate and available.	0.680
It suggests the use of modern teaching methods.	0.715
Teaching methods are appropriate, depending on the objectives and philosophy of the program.	0.745
It gives teachers autonomy to adapt their activities according to the needs of their pupils.	0.764
The organization of matter provides cross-capability.	0.626

The final questionnaire is comprised of two sections. The first section, which pertains to the pedagogical perceptions of teachers, employs 17 statements. These statements were selected with the objective of elucidating the pedagogical perceptions of teachers and were adapted to align with the specific characteristics of the Greek educational system. The statements address the following key areas:

- Students need praise, good grades, or other rewards in order to learn effectively (B1).
- Learning occurs when there is a measurable change in student behavior (B2).
- For the most effective learning, students' errors should be minimized and successes maximized (B3).
- Learning is growing through the accumulation of information (B4).
- Students learn best when they have the opportunity to observe a demonstration or example of what is being taught (B5).
- The best learning occurs when students discover answers to questions and problems themselves rather than having the answers told to them (R_C1).
- It is important to help students organize their thinking by teaching them general concepts (or schemes) before they learn more specific information (R_C2).

- Meaningful learning occurs, when students mentally create knowledge structures (schemes or concepts) by combining new ideas with their prior knowledge (existing schemes or concepts) (R_C3).
- Learning involves conscious decision-making (R_C4).
- Teachers must be active knowledge mediators (R_C5).
- Learning is based on students' mental processes (R_C6).
- Teachers should plan the teaching so that students learn in simple, forward-looking steps (R_C7).
- The teacher should be a facilitator of learning rather than a presenter of knowledge (S_C1).
- Students can be trusted to find their own goals and should be given choices as to what and how they will learn (S_C2).
- Learning increases through interaction with others (S_C3).
- Collaborative learning is an effective way to enhance student learning (S_C4).
- Teaching offers meta-cognitive skills (S_C5).

The section of the questionnaire about teacher beliefs towards the curriculum comprised ten hypotheses pertaining to the general characteristics and the subsequent impact on both the students and the teaching methodology employed:

- It caters to the different needs of all students, (Cu1).
- It is appealing to the pupils, (Cu2).
- It promotes positive social relations, (Cu3).
- The activities proposed are related to students' daily life, (Cu4).
- It offers alternative assessment capabilities, (Cu5).
- The learning and information sources defined are adequate, appropriate and available, (Cu6).
- It suggests the use of modern teaching methods, (Cu7).
- Teaching methods are appropriate, depending on the objectives and philosophy of the program, (Cu8).
- It gives teachers autonomy to adapt their activities according to the needs of their pupils, (Cu9).
- The organization of matter provides interdisciplinary capacity, (Cu10).

Furthermore, independent variables are employed to ascertain demographic factors, including gender, age, and specialty, grade of service, school type, educational region, work experience, degree, pedagogical training, and ICT training.

7. Third phase

The third phase of the research tested the factorial validity of the four factors, the 27-item TBMQ_TL derived from the second phase. Furthermore, it aimed to yield further evidence concerning reliability and validity issues. Table 2 displays the internal consistency and means of the third phase.

Table 2. Internal consistency, and means for each factor (3rd phase)

Factors	Cronbach's α	Mean	SD
Behaviorism	0.75	2.93	0.569
Radical constructivism	0.83	4.08	0.370
Social constructivism	0.75	4.09	0.440
Curriculum	0.90	3.02	0.671

Note: Items in scale: 1 = Strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = neither Agree nor Disagree; 4 = Agree; 5 = Strongly Agree

The principal factor analysis yielded a factor structure of the scale, which was subsequently tested through the use of confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) with Jamovi 2.3.28. The discrepancy between the model-reproduced covariance and the actual covariance is evaluated through the use of the chi-square statistic (Kahn, 2006). Although the chi-squared statistic was not significant, indicating an acceptable level of model fit, two limitations exist in this absolute fit index. A further limitation is the sensitivity of the chi-squared statistic to large sample sizes. Therefore, a non-significant χ^2 is improbable (Kline, 2005; Meyers, et al., 2006). Researchers have proposed the ratio of chi-square to degrees of freedom (χ^2/df) as a potential solution to the aforementioned limitations. Kline (2005) posits that a reasonable fit of the model is indicated by a low value of χ^2/df , which should fall within the range of 2.0 to 5.0. The Confirm-

atory Factor Analysis (CFA) indicated that the four-factor, 27-element model is within the acceptable limit. The observed data exhibited lambda values greater than .50 at $p < .05$, indicating that the coefficient of factor pattern/structure is a robust indicator of the latent variable (Stevens, 2002). The final execution model demonstrated an improved and acceptable fit to the observed data, as indicated by the χ^2/df ratio of 2.95, GFI of .901, NNFI of .85, CFI of .90, RMSEA of .055, and SRMR of .046. Although the NNFI value is slightly below the ideal threshold, it remains within an acceptable range for models in the social sciences, particularly in studies with complex constructs. Factor loadings ranged from .580 to .770 and they are all statistically significant ($p < .05$).

In accordance with the recommendations set forth by Bacon, Sauer, and Young (1995), composite reliability was assessed for each of the four factors. The Cronbach alpha coefficients for the four factors were as follows: Behaviorism (.75), Radical Constructivism (.83), Social Constructivism (.76), and Curriculum (.90). The CR coefficients were deemed to be satisfactory in comparison to the standard value of .70 (Nunnally, 1978).

Table 3. Composite reliability of the four-factor 27-item scale

	Behaviorism	Radical constructivism	Social constructivism	Curriculum
Composite reliability	0.75	0.83	0.76	0.90

8. Discussion

The objective of this study was to devise a valid and reliable instrument for the self-evaluation of teachers' pedagogical beliefs in conjunction with their beliefs towards the curriculum. The final four-factor structure demonstrated satisfactory psychometric properties. The items were removed on the basis of low rates of agreement. The second phase of the study entailed the reduction of one additional factor pertaining to the theoretical framework and context of the four factors. This was due to the fact that some of these factors lacked a clear structural framework. Consequently, the authors resolved that only those factors and items that demonstrated robust loading on their respective factors should be retained on the scale. This resulted in the creation of a 27-item TBMQ_TL questionnaire comprising four thematic units (behaviorism, radical constructivism, social constructivism, and curriculum) with a minimum of five items per unit. The factor structure of the final 27-item TBMQ_TL was confirmed by the third phase of the research. The latter yielded satisfactory evidence that the main constructs of the four-factor model hypothesized to underpin the research are captured.

The exploratory approach to the curriculum by education level does not demonstrate a statistically significant difference in their general characteristics or their impact on the students' learning process. Nevertheless, a notable statistical discrepancy is evident in their implementation within the pedagogical context. The data processing indicates that teachers of primary education exhibit a more favorable attitude than their counterparts in secondary education. In general, the results of the statistical analysis indicate that teachers have concerns regarding the structure and implementation of the curriculum in the educational process. The limited time available to cover the intended material, the inability to meet the diverse needs of the pupils, the lack of opportunities to foster creativity and the absence of positive relationships all contribute to a curriculum that fails to facilitate the learning process. Teachers are intimately acquainted with the pedagogical approach known as "frontal teaching," which places a premium on the teacher as the primary disseminator of knowledge. Dagdilelis (2018) notes the absence of evidence regarding the utilization of pedagogical approaches that facilitate pupil initiative. The author identifies this as a significant issue that necessitates a comprehensive and multifaceted approach to resolution.

In general, the objective of the lesson, the students and the learning environment are the key factors that influence teachers' practices. Consequently, the interdependencies between their results are consistently overlooked. This study corroborates the substantial support for the validity and reliability of the TBMQ_TL, while simultaneously reflecting the participants' responses, namely, their pedagogical beliefs regarding their own teaching practices. It is important to note that there can be discrepancies between the perceptions of what constitutes effective learning held by teachers and those held by researchers who design studies. Similar difficulties were encountered by Harrison (1987) when attempting to align the findings of her research on effective teaching with her pedagogical practices. Further research may be required to gain insight into the underlying reasons behind teachers' beliefs and the rationale behind their pedagogical choices.

9. Conclusions and implications

Theoretically, this study contributes to the literature by providing a multidimensional model that integrates pedagogical theories with attitudes toward the curriculum. It confirms that teacher beliefs are not isolated constructs but are shaped by both personal philosophical profiles and the institutional framework of the school system. In practice, the TBMQ_TL serves as a vital reference point for ongoing professional development. For educators, it serves as a reflective instrument, assisting them in aligning their pedagogical practices with their stated objectives. The tool can be utilized by school coordinators to identify particular training and development requirements amongst staff members with a view to enhancing the quality of instruction. For policymakers, it provides empirical evidence regarding how the curriculum is perceived and implemented, facilitating more informed decisions for future educational reforms.

The subsequent phase in the research process may involve the integration of self-assessment with alternative assessment methodologies, such as systematic observation, thereby encompassing the diverse perspectives of stakeholders, including students, parents, and the community. These pursuits could aid in the formulation of detailed decisions that lead to effective improvement in teacher training, thereby increasing the overall quality and range of education from this point onwards.

Consequently, a most recognizable input and initiative for meaningful changes put forth by Antoniou and Karavakou (2017) in the activities of the Greek education sector. These are proposals that pin education research and policy, apart from any statistical significance or accurately, as caught in a vicious circle of sheer formalism, bereft of any consideration for true education and contemporary educational culture.

10. Limitations

The TBMQ_TL has the potential to enhance pedagogical practice. However, a single measure is insufficient for gauging the multifaceted impact of teachers on student learning and development, as well as the broader context of their schools. Furthermore, this study did not delve into the alignment between teachers' beliefs and their practices, nor their relationship with student outcomes. Addressing this gap would require a phenomenological approach grounded in qualitative insights. The implementation of methodologies such as interviews or the observation of the educational process in the classroom would serve as a reliable complement to the relationship between beliefs and practices.

References

- Airasian, P. W., & Gullickson, A. W. (1997). *Teacher self-evaluation tool kit*. Thousand Oaks, Corwin Press.
- Anderson, R. (2008). Implications of the information and knowledge society for education. In: J. Voogt & G. Knezek (Eds.), *International handbook of information technology in primary and secondary education*, 5-22. Springer.
- Anderson, T., & Dron, J. (2011). Three generations of distance education pedagogy. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 12(3), 80–97. <https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v12i3.890>
- Antoniou, K., & Karavakou, V. (2017). Education in crisis: Reflections on the contribution of phenomenology to modern educational and political culture. In: *Pädagogik - Phänomenologie*, 209-223. Springer.
- Applefield, J. M., Huber, R., & Moallem, M. (2000). Constructivism in theory and practice: Toward a better understanding. *The High School Journal*, 84(2), 35–53.
- Bacon, D. R., Sauer, P. L., & Young, M. (1995). Composite reliability in structural equations modeling. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 55, 394–406. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013164495055003003>
- Bagakis, G. (Ed.) (2004). *The teacher and the curriculum*. Metaixmio, (in Greek).
- Blank, R. K. (2002). Using surveys of enacted curriculum to advance evaluation of instruction in relation to standards. *Peabody Journal of Education*, 77(4), 86–121. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15327930PJE7704_5
- Churchill, G. A. (1979). A paradigm for developing better measures of marketing constructs. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 16(1), 64-73. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3150876>
- Coakes, S. J., & Steed, L. G. (1999). *SPSS: Analysis without anguish*. Wiley.
- Dagdilelis, V. (2018). Preparing Teachers for the Use of Digital Technologies in their Teaching Practice. *Research in Social Sciences and Technology (RESSAT)*, 3(1), 109-121. <http://www.ressat.org/index.php/ressat/article/view/345/33>
- Epstein, R. M., & Hundert, E. M. (2002). Defining and assessing professional competence. *JAMA: Journal of the American Medical Association*, 287, 226-235. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.287.2.226>
- Garrison, D. R., & Vaughan, N. (2008). *Blended learning in higher education: Framework, principles, and guidelines*. John Wiley & Sons.

- Gergen, K. J. (1994). *Realities and relationships: Soundings in social construction*. Harvard University Press.
- Graham, G. (2008). *Teaching children physical education: Becoming a master teacher* (3rd Ed.). Champaign, IL: Human Kinetics.
- Greenhalgh, T., Wong, G., Westhorp, G., & Pawson, R. (2011). Protocol-realist and meta-narrative evidence synthesis: Evolving Standards (RAMESES). *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 11(115). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2288-11-115>
- Hair, J. F., Anderson, R. E., Tatham, R. L., & Black, W. C. (1995). *Multivariate data analysis* (4th Ed.). Prentice Hall.
- Harrison, J. (1987). A review of the research on teacher effectiveness and its implications for current practice. *Quest*, 39, 35–55.
- Jonassen, D. H. (1999). Designing constructivist learning environments. In C. M. Reigeluth (Ed.), *Instructional-design theories and models: A new paradigm of instructional theory*, Vol. II, 215–239. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Kahn, J. H. (2006). Factor analysis in counseling psychology research, training, and practice: Principles, advances, and applications. *The Counseling Psychologist*, 34(5), 684–718. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1177/0011000006286347>
- Kaiser, H. F., & Rice, J. (1974). Little Jiffy, Mark IV. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 34(1), 111–117. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001316447403400115>
- Kane, M. T. (1992). The assessment of professional competence. *Evaluation & the Health Professions*, 15, 163-182. <https://doi.org/10.1177/016327879201500203>
- Karagiorgi, Y., & Symeou, L. (2005). Translating constructivism into instructional design: Potential and limitations. *Educational Technology & Society*, 8, 17-27.
- Katsarou, E., & Dedouli, M. (2008). *Training and evaluation in education*. Pedagogical Institute (in Greek).
- Keller, C. L., & Duffy, M. (2005). "I said that?" How to improve your instructional behavior in just 5 minutes per day through data-based self-evaluation. *Teaching Exceptional Children*, 37(4), 36–39.
- Klieme, E., Hartig, J., & Rauch, D. (2008). The concept of competence in educational contexts. In J. Hartig, E. Klieme, & D. Leutner (Eds.), *Assessment of competencies in educational contexts*, 3–22. Hogrefe & Huber.
- Kline, R. B. (2005). *Principles and practice of structural equation model* (2nd Ed.). Guilford.
- Lomas, L. (2017). Knowledge, Beliefs, And Innovative Curriculum. In A. Downton, S. Livy, & J. Hall (Eds.), *40 years on: We are still learning! Proceedings of the 40th Annual Conference of the Mathematics Education, Research Group of Australasia* 357-364. MERGA.
- Matsagouras, E. (2011). *Theory and practice of teaching*. Gutenberg, (in Greek).
- Mawer, M. (1995). *The effective teaching of physical education*. Longman.
- Meyers, L. S., Gamst, G., & Guarino, A. J. (2006). *Applied multivariate research—Design and interpretation*. Thousand Oaks, Sage.
- Nunnally, J. C. (1978). *Psychometric theory* (2nd Ed.). New York, NY: McGraw-Hill.
- Peterson, K. D. (2000). *Teacher evaluation: A comprehensive guide to new directions and practices*. Thousand Oaks, Corwin Press.
- Protheroe, N. (2004). NCLB dismisses research vital to effective teaching. *Education Digest*, 69, 27–30.
- Sass, E. J. (2003). Your emerging theory / Philosophy of teaching and learning. Accessed the 30th of March 2025, at 12:10. <http://www.eds-resources.com/youremergingtheory.htm>
- Skinner, B. F. (1953). *Science and Human Behavior*. Macmillan.
- Slavin, R. E. (2020). *Educational Psychology: Theory and Practice* (12th Ed.). Pearson
- Stevens, J. P. (2002). *Applied multivariate statistics for the social sciences* (4th Ed.). Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Tabachnick, B. G., & Fidell, L. S. (2007). *Using multivariate statistics* (5th Ed.). Pearson.
- Voogt, J. (2003). Consequences of ICT for aims, contents, processes and environments of learning. In J. van den Akker, W. Kuiper & U. Hameyer (Eds.), *Curriculum landscapes and trends*, 217-236. Kluwer.
- Weber, R. P. (1990). *Basic content analysis*. Sage.
- Weinert, F. E. (2001). A concept of competence: A conceptual clarification. In D. S. Rychen & L. H. Salganik (Eds.), *Defining and selecting key competencies*, 45–65. Hogrefe & Huber.
- Woolfolk, A. (2019). *Educational Psychology* (13th Ed.). Pearson.

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